

Assay of some biologically active antimetabolite antineoplastic drugs with *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent

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In the present investigation a simple, sensitive, selective, quick and convenient method has been developed for the determination of some antimetabolite drugs e.g. methotrexate, mercaptopurine and 5-fluorouracil in pure form and in their pharmaceutical preparations.

Antimetabolites are known to exhibit a wide range of pharmacological properties and biological activities such as anticancer, antitumor, antioxidant, antinociceptive, anti-inflammatory and immunomodulating activities¹. Due to great medicinal value their analysis needs prime attention. In the present investigation we describe a simple, convenient, versatile and efficient method for the determination of antimetabolite drugs with *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established after studying the effect of variables such as reaction time, concentration and amount of reagent and reaction temperature. Variation in reaction time was found to influence the recovery. The effect of concentration of the reagent was studied and indicated the recommended concentration as (0.02 *N*). To increase reactivity of the reagent, an ionising medium was found to be necessary. The best results were obtained with glacial acetic acid. Without adding acetic acid the reaction is very slow and incomplete. The effect of volume of 0.02 *N* *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent was also varied. It was found that 5 ml of 0.02 *N*-bromosuccinimide gave accurate results. The best recovery of the sample was obtained at room temperature (25–27°C). Higher temperature (30–100°C) gives inaccurate results because of decomposition of the reagent and at lower temperature (5–20°C) the reaction is very slow.

The stoichiometric ratio of the reaction with the sample was established for each compound by reacting the sample with different concentrations of the reagent for varying reaction time. On the basis of stoichiometry and available literature, a possible course of reaction has been suggested for methotrexate [*N*-(4-{2,4-diamino pteridin-6-yl-methyl}-

methylamino)benzoyl-L-glutamic acid], and 6-mercaptopurine; [6-purinethiol] and 5-fluorouracil[5-fluoropyrimidine-2,4-dione].

In case of methotrexate, it has been noted that 4 moles of *N*-bromosuccinimide were consumed under the prescribed reaction conditions. On the basis of the nature of the reagent and the structure of the compound, the following reaction may be proposed :

In the series of purine analogues, 5-mercaptopurines also gives corresponding brominated products by consuming 2 moles of *N*-bromosuccinimide.

The pyrimidine analogues, 5-fluorouracil (2,4-dihydroxy-5-fluoropyrimidine) consumed 1 mole of *N*-bromosuccinimide and gives brominated product.

Table 1. Determination of some antimetabolite in pure form and their pharmaceutical preparations, with 0.02 *N*, *N*-bromosuccinimide reagent in acidic medium

Sl. no.	Sample	Aliquots taken (ml)	Amount present (mg)	Reaction time (min)	Molarity	Amount obtained by calculation ^a (mg)	Error (%)	SD (mg)	CV (%)
1.	Methotrexate (Pure)	5.00	5.00	5	4	4.9775	-0.45	0.00084	0.0168
	(a) Biotrezate (Injection)	5.00	4.74	5	4	4.7182	-0.46	0.00081	0.0171
	(b) Metrorex (Injection)	5.00	4.85	5	4	4.8271	-0.47	0.00111	0.0229
	(c) Neotrexate (Tablets)	5.00	4.50	5	4	4.4778	-0.49	0.00131	0.0293
	(d) Zexate (Tablets)	5.00	4.50	5	4	4.473	-0.59	0.00022	0.0049
2.	6-Mercaptopurine (Pure)	5.00	5.00	5	2	4.952	-0.96	0.00029	0.0058
	(a) Puri-nethol (Tablets)	5.00	4.88	5	2	4.879	-0.02	0.00219	0.0448
	(b) Mercapthol (Tablets)	5.00	4.88	5	2	4.854	-0.54	0.00013	0.0268
	(c) Zypurin (Tablets)	5.00	4.93	5	2	4.9210	-0.18	0.00155	0.0315
	(d) Empurine (Tablets)	5.00	4.97	5	2	4.9630	-0.14	0.00102	0.0205
3.	5-Flourouracil (Pure)	5.00	5.00	5	1	4.9840	-0.32	0.00041	0.0082
	(a) Fivoflu vial (Injection)	5.00	5.00	5	1	4.9940	0.12	0.00182	0.0364
	(b) Fluracil (Injection)	5.00	5.00	5	1	4.9765	0.47	0.00110	0.0221
	(c) Fludin (Injection)	5.00	5.00	5	1	4.984	+0.32	0.00092	0.0184
	(d) Tevafluoro (Tablets)	5.00	4.75	5	1	4.7281	-0.46	0.00081	0.0171

^aAverage of nine determinations.

Determinations can be done conveniently with 1–10 mg sample size, but for simplicity, the results are given only with 5 mg (Table 1). The value of % error, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) indicate that the proposed method is accurate. It can easily be adopted in any pharmaceutical laboratory.

Experimental

Standard solutions (0.02 *M*) of *N*-bromosuccinimide,

sodium thiosulphate, copper(II) sulphate were prepared in distilled water. Other chemicals were of reagent grade quality.

The sample solution (1 mg/ml) of pure compounds such as methotrexate, 6-mercaptopurine and 5-fluorouracil were prepared in double distilled water.

For solutions out of tablet forms, tablets were crushed to a fine powder and the powder equivalent to 100 mg of sample was taken in 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in

Note

distilled water. For injection, amount equivalent to 100 mg of the pure sample was taken and dissolved, in distilled water, in 100 ml volumetric flask. An aliquot of the sample (1–5 mg) was treated with excess *N*-bromosuccinimide and acetic acid and the unreacted reagent was estimated iodometrically.

Calculation : The amount of the sample was calculated by the following expression,

$$\text{mg of the sample} = \frac{M \times N(B - S)}{2n}$$

where, *M* = molecular weight of the sample, *N* = normality of sodium thiosulphate solution, *B* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for blank, *S* = volume of sodium thiosulphate solution for sample, *n* = number of moles of *N*-bromosuccinimide consumed per mole of the sample.

References

1. G. A. Gilman and L. S. Goodman. "In the Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 10th ed., Macmillan & Co., New York, 2001, Chap. 10, p. 215; J. V. Greenhill and P. Lue. *Prog. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **30**, 203; R. J. Suhadolnik. "Nucleosides as Biological Probes", Wiley, New York, 1979; R. Hertz. *Ann. Intern. Med.*, 1963, **59**, 931.